

RECONNAISSANCE OF GROUND-WATER QUALITY IN THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, JULY 1984

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By
René García and Michael Canoy

INTRODUCTION

The demand for ground water in the U. S. Virgin Islands, specially for domestic use has increased markedly in recent years. In 1982, ground water withdrawals for public and domestic use in the U.S. Virgin Islands were about 1.1 million gallons per day (Torres and Da Costa, 1984). Recent investigations show that additional withdrawals might be possible (F. Gómez-Gómez, USGS personal commun., 1984).

In spite of increasing demands for ground water, data on its quality is very scarce. The lack of data constitutes a major gap in the knowledge of the U.S. Virgin Islands' hydrologic environment. There are no active water-quality monitoring networks and the most recent reconnaissance was conducted nearly two decades ago (Cosner, 1972; Jordan, 1975; Jordan and Cosner, 1973; Robison, 1972).

In 1984, the U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division, conducted a reconnaissance of the ground-water quality at selected wells throughout the U.S. Virgin Islands (fig. 1). The investigation was conducted in cooperation with the Water Resources Research Institute of the College of the Virgin Islands. Wells representing the principal aquifers (fig. 2 and tables 1 to 5), were sampled for physical, chemical and bacteriological characteristics. Selected wells were also sampled to determine potential contamination with priority pollutants as designated by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). This report summarizes the data collected during the investigation (July 1984). The data will provide a base line for future investigations and an assessment of water use versus quality.

We wish to thank the U.S. National Parks Service, Public Works Department in St. Croix and St. John, and the Director of Conservation and Cultural Affairs in St. Thomas for their assistance.

Figure 1.--Geographic location of the U.S. Virgin Islands.

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Nineteen wells in the U.S. Virgin Islands (fig. 2 and tables 1 to 5), were sampled as follows: eight wells in St. Croix (map numbers 9 to 15), seven wells in St. Thomas (map numbers 1 to 7), and four wells in St. John (map numbers 16 to 19). The wells were selected to represent the most important pumping centers. The samples were collected as close as possible to the well casing. Methods described by Classen (1982), were used for the collection of the samples.

Temperature, specific conductance, pH and total alkalinity of the samples were measured at each site immediately upon collection of the samples. The depth of the water level below land surface was also determined. Samples for chemical analysis of trace elements, common ions and nutrients were collected, filtered, and preserved in accordance with procedures described by Skougstad and others (1979), and Goerlitz and Brown (1972). Samples for the determination of priority pollutants were collected at five wells (map numbers 4, 7, 13, 15, and 19), and preserved in accordance with methods established by Brown and others (1970). The samples were shipped to the U.S. Geological Survey National Water-Quality Laboratory in Doraville, Georgia, for chemical analyses. Determinations of fecal coliform and fecal streptococci bacteria were completed from raw water samples using the membrane filter method (Greeson and others, 1977). Processing and inoculation of the samples were begun in the field shortly after collection.

RESULTS

Results of the field and laboratory determinations are shown in tables 1 to 5. The principal findings of the reconnaissance were as follows:

- Specific conductance values normally ranged from 1,400 to 3,000 micromhos per centimeter (umhos/cm). Well numbers 6 and 9 had values which surpassed 4,500 umhos/cm.
- Fecal coliform and fecal streptococci bacteria were detected in samples from 18 of the 19 wells sampled. Colony counts of fecal streptococci bacteria were as high as 5,800 colonies/100 milliliters (mL) of raw water sampled.
- Nitrate concentrations exceeded 1.0 milligrams per liter (mg/L) at ten of the wells sampled.
- Chloride concentrations generally ranged from 180 to 600 mg/L. At 13 wells (map numbers 1, 4, 5 thru 8, 10, 12, 13, 15, 17, and 18), chloride concentrations exceeded drinking water standards of 250 mg/L (EPA Drinking Water Regulations).
- Sulfate concentrations for most wells were less than the drinking water standard of 250 mg/L. All the wells sampled had total dissolved solids exceeding the EPA secondary drinking water standard of 500 mg/L.
- Concentrations of organic compounds and most trace elements at selected sites were less than detection limits.

Additional information about the wells sampled and the data in this report is available from the U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division, Caribbean District office in San Juan, Puerto Rico (Tel. (809) 753-4414).

EXPLANATION
 COASTAL EMBAYMENT AQUIFER
 VOLCANIC ROCKS AQUIFER
 KINGSHILL AQUIFER
 WELL SITE
 PRIORITY POLLUTANTS SAMPLED WELL SITE

Figure 2.--Principal aquifers and selected wells sampled in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Table 1.--Physical, chemical, and bacteriological characteristics from selected wells in the U.S. Virgin Islands, July 1984.

WELL NUMBER ON MAP	LOCATION (LAT/LONG)	WELL NAME	OPERATED BY	DWL (FT)	T (DEG C)	SC (UMHOS /CM)	pH (UNITS)	ALK	FC	FS	NO2	NO2-NO3	PO4	TOC
1	17425644758	Golden Grove no. 1	DPW	36.75	29.0	1725	7.4	574	K 8	1	0.255	0.750	0.040	1.0
2	17430864484	Adventure no. 16	DPW	40.74	33.0	1750	7.6	531	< 1	< 1	.190	.710	.014	3.4
3	17425864522	Prosperity no. 1	DPW	34.83	28.5	1325	7.0	316	< 1	K 4	.025	1.1	.001	1.2
4	17432964454	Barron Spot no. 6	DPW	70.96	27.5	3175	7.6	597	< 1	K 2	.016	1.0	.015	.8
5	17422564479	Fairplains no. 5	DPW	58.07	27.5	5750	7.0	489	< 1	< 1	.016	.687	.071	.9
6	17452764460	Concordia no. 1	DPW	25.27	27.5	2975	7.0	458	< 1	4.0	.015	.710	.013	.9
7	17465964476	Rust-up-twist	PO	32.13	27.0	2550	7.4	500	K 4	5800	.030	.850	.052	.8
8	17452664371	Zell's Well	PO	78.93	32.5	4675	7.2	446	38	2300	.016	.940	.014	.9
9	18203364531	V.I.H.A. no. 2	VIMA	73.86	29.0	1150	7.0	602	1	65	.008	ND	.009	1.7
10	18191364530	Bavoni no. 2	PO	24.37	28.5	2350	7.2	554	< 1	370	.011	8.0	.009	2.4
11	18203664581	C.V.I. no. 2	CVI	46.83	29.0	1250	7.4	485	1	94	.007	5.8	.011	1.1
12	18214164574	Agriculture Station	USDA	65.15	25.5	1900	7.1	448	1	23	.009	3.1	.054	1.0
13	18194564525	Polycarib no. 3	PO	118.27	28.0	2425	7.2	530	1	K 488	.016	2.3	.003	3.8
14	18213064574	Bryan's Well no. 2	PO	ND	25.5	1250	6.9	251	K 36	4	.006	2.8	.065	7
15	18214264542	Mohagony Run no. 9	PO	81.70	28.0	2230	6.8	580	< 1	4700	< .001	< .010	< .001	2.0
16	18211264451	N.P.S. no. 9	USNPS	ND	27.0	1925	6.8	518	< 1	10	.005	.597	.009	1.2
17	18205864432	Carolina Well	DPW	5.82	27.5	2000	6.8	287	6	109	.008	1.2	.012	1.2
18	18201064478	N.P.S. no. 2	USNPS	27.75	29.0	2500	7.0	560	50	3900	.011	4.9	.012	2.0
19	18204364456	Sussanaberg no. 5	DPW	62.89	25.5	1450	7.0	538	5	8	< .001	1.6	.007	1.7

EXPLANATION

DWL - Depth to water level below land surface, in feet
 T - Temperature, in degrees Celsius
 SC - Specific conductance, in micromhos per centimeter at 25°C
 ALK - Total alkalinity as calcium carbonate, in milligrams per liter
 FC - Fecal coliform bacteria, in colonies per 100 milliliters
 FS - Fecal streptococci bacteria, in colonies per 100 milliliters
 DPW - Virgin Islands Department of Public Works
 VIMA - Virgin Islands Housing Authority
 USDA - United States Department of Agriculture
 NO2 - Nitrite as nitrogen, total
 NO2 + NO3 - Nitrite plus nitrate as nitrogen, total
 PO4 - Phosphorus, orthophosphate
 TOC - Organic carbon, total
 TDS - Total dissolved solids
 -- - No data
 PO - Privately operated
 CVI - College of the Virgin Islands
 USNPS - United States National Park Service

Table 2.--Concentrations of dissolved common ions and trace elements from selected wells in the U.S. Virgin Islands, July 1984.

WELL NUMBER ON MAP	COMMON IONS, DISSOLVED (MILLIGRAMS PER LITER)										TRACE METALS, TOTAL (MICROGRAMS PER LITER)									
	Ca	Mg	Na	K	SO4	Cl	F	SiO2	TDS	As	Ba	Cd	Cr	Pb	Hg	Se	Ag			
1	67	48	280	0.9	99	270	0.6	47	1150	2	100	1	2	2	1.7	3	< 1			
2	37	36	250	.5	55	190	.6	38	919	2	< 100	1	2	2	0.6	2	< 1			
3	100	29	92	.7	33	170	.5	37	610	2	100	1	6	2	0.5	1	< 1			
4	21	10	590	8.0	170	460	.9	28	1640	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--			
5	220	10	750	2.7	270	1500	.5	40	3190	2	200	1	2	1	0.6	4	1			
6	120	65	420	6.4	190	600	.6	36	1670	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--			
7	35	42	440	1.3	55	490	.8	38	1390	1	< 100	1	< 1	1	0.4	1	< 1			
8	120	81	670	7.2	220	1100	.8	33	2460	1	< 100	< 1	< 1	< 1	1.4	8	< 1			
9	71	46	230	1.1	61	160	.8	45	977	1	< 100	1	5	3	< 0.1	2	< 1			
10	66	83	340	2.3	99	440	.5	46	1410	1	< 100	1	5	1	0.2	3	< 1			
11	39	32	230	.9	44	180	.8	48	861	1	< 100	1	1	1	0.3	3	< 1			
12	37	24	330	.8	72	330	.3	34	1090	1	< 100	1	3	< 1	0.5	2	< 1			
13	40	43	370	1.9	90	410	.7	27	1320	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--			
14	16	13	220	.8	32	230	.3	35	696	1	< 100	1	4	1	0.3	1	< 1			
15	180	62	280	6.9	200	390	1.1	33	1460	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--			
16	77	64	230	3.3	42	370	.5	36	1120	1	< 100	1	4	1	0.4	1	< 1			
17	41	46	290	3.2	120	430	.3	36	1140	1	< 100	1	5	< 1	0.5	1	< 1			
18	100	75	360	2.2	67	490	.5	38	1460	1	< 100	2	6	1	0.6	< 1	< 1			
19	66	54	180	3.2	30	180	.6	40	869	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--			

EXPLANATION

Ca - Calcium
 Mg - Magnesium
 Na - Sodium
 K - Potassium
 SO4 - Sulfate
 Cl - Chloride
 F - fluoride
 SiO2 - Silica
 TDS - Total dissolved solids
 As - Arsenic
 Ba - Barium
 Cd - Cadmium
 Cr - Chromium
 Pb - Lead
 Hg - Mercury
 Se - Selenium
 Ag - Silver
 -- - No data

Table 3.--Concentrations of priority pollutants at selected wells in the U.S. Virgin Islands, July 1984.

WELL NUMBER ON MAP	Al	Sb	As	Be	Cd	Cr	Cu	Fe	Pb	Li	Mn	Hg	Mo	Ni	Se	Ag	Zn	CYANIDE
4	70	< 1	2	< 10	< 1	< 10	< 1	< 10	1	10	< 10	0.1	2	< 1	4	< 1	10	< 0.01
7	< 10	< 1	< 1	< 10	< 1	< 10	< 1	10	2	50	< 10	.3	< 1	2	6	< 1	10	< 0.01
14	10	< 1	--	< .5	1.2	--	11	7.7	< 10	< 4	180	--	< 10	--	--	2	13	< 0.01
16	10	< 1	< 1	< .5	1.5	--	< 10	230	< 10	< 4	17	--	< 10	--	--	1	190	< 0.01
19	20	< 1	< 1	< 10	< 1	< 10	1	< 10	1	< 4	< 10	< .1	< 1	1	1	< 1	21	< .01

EXPLANATION

Al - Aluminum
 Sb - Antimony
 As - Arsenic
 Be - Beryllium
 Cd - Cadmium
 Cr - Chromium
 Cu - Copper
 Fe - Iron
 Pb - Lead
 Li - Lithium
 Mn - Manganese
 Hg - Mercury
 Mo - Molybdenum
 Ni - Nickel
 Se - Selenium
 Ag - Silver
 Zn - Zinc
 -- - No data

Table 4.--Purgeable organic, base-neutral, and acid extractable compounds for which analyses were performed in samples from five wells in the U.S. Virgin Islands, July 1984.

Minimum detection limit 3.0 micrograms per liter			
Benzene	1,1-Dichloroethane	Tetrachloroethylene	
Bromoform	1,2-Dichloroethane	Toluene	
Carbon tetrachloride	1,1-Dichloroethylene	1,1,1-trichloroethane	
Chlorobenzene	1,2-trans-Dichloroethylene	1,1,2-Trichloroethane	
Chloroethane	1,2-Dichloropropane	Trichloroethylene	
2-Chloroethyl vinyl ether	1,3-Dichloropropene	Trichlorofluoromethane	
Chloroform	Ethylbenzene	Vinyl chloride	
Dibromochloromethane	Methylbromide		
Dichlorobromomethane	Methylene chloride		
Dichlorodifluoromethane	1,1,2,2-Tetrachloroethane		
Minimum detection limit 1.0 micrograms per liter			
Acenaphthene	Chrysene	Hexachlorobutadiene	2,4-Dichlorophenol
Acenaphthylene	Dibenzo (a,h) anthracene	Hexachlorocyclopentadiene	2,4-Dimethylphenol
Anthracene	1,2-Dichlorobenzene	Hexachloroethane	4,6-Dinitro-2-methylphenol
Benzo (a) anthracene	1,3-Dichlorobenzene	Indeno (1,2,3) pyrene	2,4-Dinitrophenol
Benzo (b) fluoranthene	1,4-Dichlorobenzene	Isophorone	2-Nitrophenol
Benzo (k) fluoranthene	Diethyl phthalate	Naphthalene	4-Nitrophenol
Benzo (g,h,i) perylene	Dimethyl phthalate	Nitrobenzene	2,4-Dichlorophenol
Benzo (a) pyrene	Di-n-butyl phthalate	n-Nitrosodi-n-propylamine	Phenol
4-Bromophenyl phenyl ether	2,4-Dinitrotoluene	n-Nitrosodimethylamine	2,4,6-Trichlorophenol
Butyl benzyl phthalate	2,6-Dinitrotoluene	n-Nitrosodiphenylamine	2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorophenol
bis (2-Chloroethoxy) methane	Di-n-octylphthalate	Phenanthrene	4-Bromophenyl phenol
bis (2-Chloroethyl) ether	bis (2-Ethylhexyl)phthalate	Pyrene	3,3-Dichlorobenzid
bis (2-Chloroisopropyl) ether	Fluoranthene	1,2,4-Trichlorobenzene	
2-Chloronaphthalene	Fluorene	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol	
4-Chlorophenyl phenyl ether	Hexachlorobenzene	2-Chlorophenol	

All concentrations were below minimum detection level.

Table 5. Organochlorine insecticides, polychlorinated biphenyls, and polychlorinated naphthalenes for which analyses were performed in samples from five wells in the U.S. Virgin Islands, July 1984.

Minimum detection level 0.01 micrograms per liter	
ALDRIN	
DDD	
DEE	
DDT	
DIELDRIN	
ENDRIN	
ENDOSULFAN	
HEPTACHLOR	
HEPTACHLOR EPOXIDE	
LINDANE	
METHOXYCHLOR	
MIREX	
Minimum detection level 0.1 micrograms per liter	
CHLORDANE	
GROSS POLYCHLORINATED BIPHENYLS (AS PCB)	
GROSS POLYCHLORINATED NAPHTHALENES (AS PCN)	
AROCHLOR 1016	
AROCHLOR 1221	
AROCHLOR 1232	
AROCHLOR 1242	
AROCHLOR 1248	
AROCHLOR 1254	
AROCHLOR 1260	
PERTHANE	
Minimum detection level 1.0 micrograms per liter	
TOXAPHENE	

All concentrations were below minimum detection level.

REFERENCES

Brown, E., and others, 1970, Methods for the collection and analysis of water samples for dissolved minerals and gases: U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water Resources Investigations, Book 5, Chapter A1,